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Open and Available Online Academic Databases for Library and Information Services from the Perspective of Developing Nations

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Abstract

The Information and Communication Technology (ICT) dispensation has ushered in a transformation characterized by open access initiatives, which has added a new dimension to how libraries manage scholarly content most especially Academics in a developing nation. This paper highlights open-access online databases which are freely available over the internet. The paper further elaborates on the concepts, types, and factors affecting access to online open-access databases in developing nations. Several authors critiqued open access initiatives to be fostering lowly quality publication, but the benefit of open access initiatives cannot be overemphasized due to its provision of unlimited access to information for developing nations.

Keyword: Open Access, Databases, Library, ICT

Introduction

ICT adoption in library services has changed the pattern of information handling and transformed the nature of service delivery in the library. ICT has enhanced and improved the way library services are offered, it has changed the concept of the library from a storehouse to a knowledge management center. Nowadays Libraries use various technologies to perform library operations and provide Library services (Shehu et al, 2020). The most prominent of the information services offered by ICTs is the Database oriented services. Libraries have played a prominent role in disseminating information, and providing end users with access to information sources through the library shelves and now, by electronic means. The introduction of the Internet and Databases to library and information services has greatly enhanced the efficiency and effectiveness of information services. Thus, books and journals that have hitherto been easy to keep current in research and academic libraries of developing countries are now available electronically as soon as they are published (Abdulkadir & Nock,2011). The utilization of electronic resources is in vogue, especially in developed nations, and recently developing nations are realizing the importance of ICT and are consequently utilizing E-resources but are marred with challenges such as Funding, constant Power outage, Lack of skills, Lack of awareness, etc. Going further research has shown that the awareness and utilization of Open Academic Database are low especially in developing nations like Nigeria, which necessitates this paper to guide students, faculty members, and researchers to have the knowledge of various open and available databases relevant in an academic setting thereby eliminating the need for expensive database subscription.

Concepts of Open Online Database

Kathiravav (2018) gave the concept of open access as resources readily available, free of charge, and accessible online and at the same time available for subsequent re-use, in the same vein he asserts that free access is a type of content that can be accessed for free but is not necessarily available for re-use or re-distribution. Open Access (2022) defined Open Access as a set of “principles and a range of practices through which research outputs are distributed online, free of access charges or other barriers” (Para 1).

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The Berlin Declaration on “Open Access to Knowledge states that establishing open access as a worthwhile procedure ideally requires the active commitment of every individual producer of scientific knowledge and holder of cultural heritage. Open access contributions include original scientific research results, raw data and metadata, source materials, digital representations of pictorial and graphical materials, and scholarly multimedia material” (Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities, 2003).

The Budapest Open Access Initiative definition, which is vivid, explains “open access” as scholarly publications that are freely available on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself (Budapest Open Access Initiative, 2002).

According to Techopedia (2022) the definition of online databases is computers and their peripherals connected to a network such as an intranet or with global view internet. The website further elaborates that online activity is an adjective to describe an activity performed while on the internet. Going further Kopal (2015) as cited in Irogonachi and Izuagbe (2018) The development of databases started in the 1950s and bibliographical databases started in the 1960s. initially, before the advent of ICT, Index card was used by Library and Information science professionals to store data without recourse to organization and retrieval techniques. CD-ROM database first emanated in the late 1980s, In the 21st century, ICT penetration brought about the development of Online databases. Daniel (2010) gave the concept of a Database as an organized collection of metadata for one or more multiple uses. In the same vein (Gray 1976) cited in Irogonachi and Izuagbe (2018) defined a Database as an organized collection of information or data usually in computer-readable form. They went further to elaborate that databases are available in online or offline search services. These search services have computers and software that facilitate the retrospective search of one or more databases to locate information or references in answer to a specific query. Databases are mostly characterized by the kind of data they contain which may be words, numbers, or subject matter. Whereas word-oriented databases contain words or text as the principal data, numbers-oriented databases are often referred to as databanks and they contain numbers, symbols, series, graphs, and tables. The Glossary of Library and Information Science gave the concept of the online database as "An electronic database of either full-text documents or citations and abstracts which can be searched by telephone or internet". In the same context, Verma (2016) gave the concept of “Online Database as a search is that is performed by an individual scholar or librarian using a computer and the internet. By connecting with a database research service, millions of records from thousands of publications in hundreds of databases can be searched for material on a topic” she further explained that an online database is accessed from a network such as the Internet, and without the networks, accessibility is compromised and that it differs from local database in which storage is in individual computers, and its peripherals such as CDs, DVDs.

Types of Online Database

Different categories and types of databases are in existence. Some literature had classified databases according to Data Models and Data types, such as Relational, Network, Hierarchical, and Object-oriented. Other categories are Centralized database, Cloud database, Distributed

database, Document Oriented database, Navigational database, Object-oriented database Relational database.

Online databases are categorized according to the huge range of different information types, which majorly fall under two categories (Upadhayay, 2016)

❖ **Reference Databases**

Reference or secondary is a type of database that covers only bibliographic references on the subject. It comprises clues to the intellectual contents and physical character of pieces of the graphic or printed record of humanity such as journals, articles, books, and research reports (Upadhayay, 2016). etc. Furthermore, Reference databases are classified into two which are:

◆ **Bibliographic Databases**

A bibliographic database is a type of database that contains bibliographic records and sometimes abstracts of literature in some instances, it entails an organized digital collection of references to published literature including journal and newspaper articles, conference proceedings and paper reports, government and legal publications, patents, books, etc. Bibliographic databases describe analytics that contains rich subject descriptions. E.g. CA SEARCH (Produced by Chemical Abstract Services), BIOSIS, INSPEC, Medline, ERIC (Educational Resources Information Centre) database.

◆ **Referral Databases**

It guides the user toward the address of a person or an organization, this type of database offers references to information or data such as names and addresses of organizations, persons, institutions, other directory types of data, and information systems etc.

❖ **Directory Databases**

This offers the information of published directories and usually the links to full directories. The directory databases may list organizations, individuals, electronic or printed publications, materials, chemical substances, computer software, and audiovisual material, etc. E.g. Electronic Yellow Pages (by market data retrieval), TriNet Database. Directory Databases are categorized as follows:

◆ **Source Databases**

These databases contain the original data sources in machine-readable form. The data are available in machine-readable as well as in printed form. It can be grouped according to its contents such as Full-Text Databases. Which contains complete Full text of information content. e.g. The New York Times via NEXIS WESTLAW (1975) a legal database by a west publishing company, Britannica Online contains entire encyclopedia articles, Lexis-Nexis provides the full-text of articles from newspapers, magazines, and other publications related to law, JSTOR Full-text periodicals covering a wide range of topics, including humanities, social sciences, and natural sciences.

◆ **Numeric Databases**

Numeric databases contain numeric data such as statistics, time series, demographic reports, corporate financial records, stock market quotations, chemical and physical properties, chemical nomenclature, and graphics structure, most numeric databases can be manipulated interactively by the users. Numeric databases also contain transactional data

(the large database called transactional databases). Example: FOREIGN EXCHANGE DATABASE (by interactive data corporation) FIU OASIS: Full text & Numeric database.

◆ **Multimedia Databases**

Multimedia databases contain a mix of different media such as text, audio, video, and still graphics (photographs, diagrams and illustration, graphs, charts, maps and even representation of works of art). These databases also include textual information used to describe the image, music, video, etc.

◆ **Dictionary Databases**

Dictionary databases are synonymous with directory databases in the sense that each record identifies something. the dictionary databases also serve to provide the measure of control in the use of bibliographic databases, for example, Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary.

Open Access Strategies

E-print archives and self-archiving institutional repositories are all initiatives toward open access (Ghosh and Das,2002). They went further to elaborate that Institutions promote open access to the research work carried out by them through establishing institutional repositories. These are digital archives of intellectual products created by the faculty, staff, and students of an institution and accessible to end users both within and outside the institution, with few if any barriers to access. Institutions may act independently or within a state or regional consortium.

BOAI (2002) put forward two primary strategies to attain open access initiatives which are:

❖ **Open Access Through Journal**

Listing and publishing free of any fee, because price is a barrier to access, therefore journals and their associated databases will not charge subscription or access fee, instead would look for other means of covering their expenses. Such as foundations, endorsements by government or other concerned bodies, Grants, etc

❖ **Open Access Through Repositories**

This practice is known as self-achieving where institution such as Universities, Polytechnics, and Monotechnic promote open access to the research work carried out by them through establishing institutional repositories. These are digital archives of intellectual products created by the faculty, staff, and students of an institution and are made accessible to end users both within and outside the institution, free of charge. This Institutions may act independently or within a state or regional consortium.

Open Access Online Databases and Repositories in Library and Information Science

Several open access online databases exist especially with the fact that several non-governmental organizations and activists are canvassing to move the world to open access e.g., UNESCO. Open Access is a movement that makes online publications immediately available free of charge and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions. This movement is being largely supported and put into practice by several countries and institutions (UNESCO, 2022). Some Open Access relevant to Library and Information services are listed below:

Open Access Journals

Open access journals are databases that index journals and, articles on various subjects such as:

❖ **DOAJ**

Directory of Open Access Journal hosts a community-curated list of open access journals, maintained by Infrastructure Services for Open Access. It was launched in 2003 with 300 open-access journals. accessible at <https://doaj.org/>

❖ **Open Access Journals**

The Open Access Journals was founded with a mission to develop a reliable platform and to provide unrestricted access to scientific literature for rapid dissemination of recent updates in various disciplines of science and technology. Readers can have access with no cost and avail of the facility to enrich their scientific understanding in the relevant topics, most especially in science and technology and medicine. It can be accessed using the link <https://www.openaccessjournals.com/>

❖ **Elsevier**

It is a Netherlands-based academic publishing company specializing in scientific, technical, and medical content. Its products include journals such as The Lancet, Cell, the ScienceDirect collection of electronic journals, Trends, the Current Opinion series, the online citation database Scopus, the SciVal tool for measuring research performance, the Clinical Key search engine for clinicians, and the Clinical Path evidence-based cancer care service. Elsevier's products and services also include digital tools for data management, instruction, research analytics, and assessment, it should be noted that not all content is free, however, the link to free content is at <https://www.elsevier.com/open-access/open-access-journals>

❖ **Sage Journals**

SAGE Open is a peer-reviewed, "Gold" open access journal from SAGE that publishes original research and review articles in an interactive, open access format. Articles may span the full spectrum of the social and behavioral sciences and the humanities and are accessible at <https://journals.sagepub.com/home/sgo>

❖ **ScienceDirect**

Indexes and publishes articles on Sciences such as Life Science, which includes but is not limited to agricultural and biological science, biochemistry, genetics, and molecular biology, environmental sciences, Immunology, Microbiology, and neurosciences. Physical sciences and engineering incorporating chemical engineering, chemistry, computer science, earth and planetary science, energy, mathematics, physics, and astronomy.

❖ **PLoS: Public Library of Science**

It is a nonprofit organization of scientists and physicians who are committed to making the world's scientific and medical literature freely available to the public. PLoS also publishes peer-reviewed, open-access scientific and medical journals that include original research as well as feature articles. It is accessible at <http://www.plos.org/>

❖ **Open Access Library (OA LIB)**

It is an Academic database based on metadata of Open Access papers, OALib is currently hosting links and metadata to more than 5,712,330 open access articles covering a wide range

of academic disciplines and readily available for download. It is accessible at <https://www.oalib.com/>

Hybrid

❖ **Oxford Academic**

Open access (OA) is a key part of Oxford University Press (OUP) its mission is to support the widest possible dissemination of high-quality research. It provides open access to both articles and books. It indexes materials on social sciences, sciences, and Law and can be accessed at <https://academic.oup.com/pages/open-research/open-access#oa-journals>

❖ **Highwire Press**

It is an initiative by Stanford university to index and digitize academic journals, and also other multimedia content and books, they try to partner with some digital publishing companies such as McGraw hill, Cambridge university press, BMJ etc. it can be accessed at <http://highwire.stanford.edu/>

❖ **Z-Library**

It is a shadow project for file-sharing access to scholarly journal articles, academic texts, and general-interest books. Most of its books are from Library Genesis while some of them are uploaded directly to its site by individuals. Individuals can also contribute to the website's repository to make literature accessible to as many people as possible. As of 24 August 2022, Z-lib states that it possesses more than 10,870,978 books and 84,837,646 articles (Wikipedia,2022) it is like the Dark web of academic publishing, it observed that librarians have been professionally silent about Z library some librarians emphasized that it does not breach the Ranganathan 5 Laws of Librarianship, therefore largely embraced. It is accessible at <https://z-lib.org/>

❖ **Library Genesis (Lib Gen)**

Library genesis is based on the same algorithm as Z-Library also a shadow file sharing database, the essence is to provide access to scholarly journals, books, and multimedia such as an audiobook, magazines, images, and comic, lib gen also aggregates links and accessible at <https://libgen.li/>

❖ **PubMed Central**

PubMed Central is a free digital archive of biomedical and life sciences journal literature at the National Institute of Health in the US. It indexes a list of journals whose contents are available in the form of open-access publications. It has many journals listed from Biomed Central, an independent publishing house with more than 160 peer-reviewed open-access journals, which can be accessed at <http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/>

❖ **AXiv e-print Archive**

Provides open access to over a million e-prints in the fields of physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, and statistics. Accessible at <https://arxiv.org/>

❖ **CiteSeerX**

CiteSeerX is a computer and information science database that is rich IT related Materials and hosted by Pennsylvania State University. Accessible at <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/index.jsessionid=3A3984195E8B05CCFFE59AE6C7B8E6C1>

Books

These are databases that index electronic books, some examples are given below:

❖ PDF Drive

PDF drive is a database that index electronic books on various subject. The database claims to have 79,542,866 eBooks and is accessible for free at <https://www.pdfdrive.com/>

❖ Cambridge University Press

Publishes several Gold “A” books and works with publishing partners such as learned societies to develop OA in different communities. It can be accessed at <https://www.cambridge.org/core/what-we-publish/open-access>

❖ National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine

It has more than 200 books a year on a wide range of topics in science, engineering, and medicine, providing authoritative, independently-researched information on important matters in science and health policy.

Factors Influencing Access to Online Open Databases

According to Adepoju et. al (2019) factors affecting the use of Online Open databases are

- Lack of Awareness
- Lack of User Education
- Unstable Electricity
- Lack of Funding to Procure ICT facilities
- Lack of ICT skill set

Conclusion

The study examined and listed some of the online open academic databases, it is notable that a lot of organizations are canvassing for open access initiatives with the information explosion, and academic libraries in developing nations are taking advantage by directing the library patrons to various databases using the ICT to satisfy their information needs. However, some authors such as Beall (2013) critiqued open access as an anti-corporatist movement that encourages young scholars and developing nations to publish in low-quality journals. He further emphasized that the open access movement has fostered the creation of predatory publishers and stand-alone journals, increasing the amount of research misconduct in scholarly publications. But what he fails to put into account is that the developing world cannot afford to subscribe to a wide array of primary literature due to limited or lack of resources, which is the reason open access is now a boom in the developing world. Therefore, open access is an alternative to varieties of resources, especially in developing nations where subscription to expensive databases such as EBSCOhost is hindered because of funding.

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